

HIGH RELIABILITY ENERGY AND COMBINED SIGNAL TRANSMISSION NETWORKS

Qarshiboyev Feruz Egamnazar og‘li¹

¹ Master of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after
Muhammad al Khorezmi

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ABSTRACT

Defects in the installation of power and signal transmission eliminate Efficient use of current generated by the power and signal transmission panel. Elimination of waste in the transmission of energy and signal generated by the transmission panel to the consumer.

Power and signal transmission panels generate free energy by converting energy and signal transmission light into electrical energy without any moving parts, zero emissions and maintenance from energy and signal transmission. Power and signal transmission batteries, a set of individual silicone cameras that generate electricity from energy and signal transmission energy. Photons (light particles) produce an electric current when they strike the surface of thin silicon wafers. A single energy and signal transmission cell produces only about 1/2 (0.5) volts. If the power and signal transmission panel can be set to 24 volt output, there will be 72 cameras, so 36 both 12 volt groups can often be connected in series, which is typically the 24 volt output of the power and signal transmission panel. allows Under load (e.g. when charging batteries), this voltage drops from 12 to 14 volts (for a 12-volt configuration) and from 75 to 100 watts for a panel of this size. It follows that in order for us to consume 220 volts during daylight hours, the battery power and signal transmission panel must produce 380-440 volts. Multiple power and signal transmission panels can be

connected in parallel via a cable to increase the available voltage (more power) and can be connected in series with wires to amplify 24, 48 and even higher voltage systems. The advantage of not using high-voltage output on power and signal transmission panels is that smaller wires can be used to transfer power from the power and signal transmission panel to chargers and batteries. Large copper cables and cables are very expensive to purchase as the body price of copper has risen sharply in the last few years. Today, there are three types of panels. These are monocrystalline energy and signal transmission panels, polycrystalline energy and signal transmission panels and amorphous energy and signal transmission panels. Monocrystalline Energy and Signal Transmission Panels: The most efficient and expensive energy and signal transmission panels are manufactured with monocrystalline cells. Energy and signal transmission films use very pure silicon and involve complex crystal growth. Longer silicone bars are produced. They are divided into discs or corrugations with a thickness of 2-4 mm, which are then processed into separate chambers connected to

each other on the power and signal transmission panels; Polycrystalline Energy and Signal Transmission Panels: Multicrystalline, energy and signal transmission panels made with polycrystalline cells are slightly less expensive and slightly less efficient because the cells are not grown in a single crystal, but are produced in a large proportion of many crystals. Gives them the appearance of clear glass. Like monocrystalline cells, they are divided into vases to produce individual cells that make up the energy and signal transmission panels; Amorphous energy and signal transmission panels: They are not really crystalline, but lay a thin layer of silicone on the base material such as metal or glass to create the energy and

signal transmission panel. These Amorphous Energy and Signal Transmission Panels are very inexpensive, but their energy efficiency requires a much smaller square footage to produce the same amount of power as a Monocrystalline or Polycrystalline Energy and Signal Transmission Panel. Amorphous energy and signal transmission panels can also be installed on long sheets of roofing material to cover large areas of the roof surface facing south. The use of amorphous energy and signal transmission panels without batteries in educational institutions and enterprises operating only during the day is much cheaper than the use of polycrystalline and monocrystalline energy and signal transmission panels.

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